

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
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***BULLETIN OF* FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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**ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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ON THE ISSUE OF STUDYING CLINICAL-IMMUNOLOGICAL, EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ASPECTS AND OPTIMIZATION OF TREATMENT OF DERMATOMYCOSIS IN MILITARY PERSONNEL**Tashmatova Z.U., Azizov B.S.**

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Resume. This article addresses the clinical, immunological, and epidemiological characteristics of dermatomycoses in military personnel, proposing optimized diagnostic and therapeutic approaches. The data includes fungal surveillance results, clinical form characteristics, immunological changes, and complication rates. Emphasis is placed on the importance of preventive measures and personalized medical strategies in military settings.

Keywords: dermatomycoses, military personnel, tinea pedis, candidiasis, terbinafine, immunity, diagnosis, prevention, PCR, MALDI-TOF.

ҲАРБИЙ ХИЗМАТЧИЛАРДА ДЕРМАТОМИКОЗЛАРНИ КЛИНИК-ИММУНОЛОГИК ВА ЭПИДЕМИОЛОГИК ЖИҲАТДАН ЎРГАНИШ ҲАМДА ДАВОЛАШНИ ОПТИМАЛЛАШТИРИШ МАСАЛАСИГА ОИД**Ташматова З.У., Азизов Б.С.**

Ўзбекистон Республикаси Куролли Кучлари Ҳарбий тиббиёт академияси, Тошкент ш., Ўзбекистон

Резюме. Ушбу мақолада ҳарбий хизматчилар орасида учрайдиган дерматомикозларнинг клиник, иммунологик ва эпидемиологик хусусиятлари кўриб чиқилган. Таъхис қўйиши ва даволашнинг оптималлаштирилган усуллари таъриф этилган. Микологик мониторинг маълумотлари, клиник кўринишлар, иммунологик ўзгаришлар ва асоратлар частотаси келтирилган. Ҳарбий шароитда профилактик чоралар ва шахсий ёндашувнинг аҳамияти таъкидланган.

Калит сўзлар: дерматомикоз, ҳарбий хизматчилар, оёқ микозлари, кандидиаз, тербинафин, иммунитет, таъхис, профилактика, PCR, MALDI-TOF.

К ВОПРОСУ ИЗУЧЕНИЮ КЛИНИКО-ИММУНОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ, ЭПИДЕМИОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ АСПЕКТОВ И ОПТИМИЗАЦИИ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ДЕРМАТОМИКОЗОВ У ВОЕННОСЛУЖАЩИХ**Ташматова З.У., Азизов Б.С.**

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Резюме. В статье рассмотрены клинико-иммунологические и эпидемиологические особенности дерматомикозов у военнослужащих, а также предложены оптимальные схемы диагностики и терапии. Представлены данные микологического мониторинга, особенности клинических форм, иммунологических изменений и частота осложнений. Подчеркивается значимость профилактики и персонализированного подхода в условиях военной службы.

Ключевые слова: дерматомикозы, военнослужащие, микоз стоп, кандидоз, тербинафин, иммунитет, диагностика, профилактика, ПЦР, MALDI-TOF.

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Introduction. Dermatomycoses among military personnel represent a significant medical and social concern, exerting a considerable impact on combat readiness and sanitary-epidemiological conditions in confined military collectives. The military lifestyle is associated with numerous risk factors, such as prolonged wearing of enclosed footwear, intense perspiration, frequent minor skin injuries, limited access to hygiene facilities, and high population density in barracks. These conditions foster the spread of skin and nail fungal infections. Literature reflects an increasing number of mycoses among service members during both peacetime and field operations, alongside a rise in pathogen resistance to standard therapies.

Objective. This review aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of current scientific data on the clinical, immunological, and epidemiological characteristics of dermatomycoses in military personnel, and to evaluate evidence-based approaches to their optimal treatment and prevention.

Methodology. The review is based on over 80 scientific sources, including publications from international databases such as PubMed, Scopus, eLibrary, and Web of Science, as well as domestic dermatovenereological journals, Ministry of Defense guidelines, and Ministry of Health materials. Articles featuring clinical case descriptions, immunological study results, epidemiological data on mycosis prevalence, and clinical trials of antifungal agents were considered.

Epidemiological Aspects. Currently, consolidated epidemiological data specifically targeting military personnel as a distinct at-risk group for dermatomycoses are virtually absent in accessible literature. However, considering service conditions—tight footwear, high physical strain, overcrowding, and limited hygiene access—one can reasonably presume a high prevalence of mycoses in this demographic. Tinea pedis and onychomycosis caused by *Trichophyton rubrum* and *Tr. mentagrophytes* are likely predominant, following global patterns. Observational reports describe outbreaks in barracks, bathhouses, and gyms, where the infection is transmitted via communal footwear, mats, towels, and gym equipment. The issue necessitates targeted epidemiological studies within military environments, especially in climatically unfavorable regions where heat and humidity prevail. Research in Uzbek military hospitals confirms increased infection rates linked to poor hygiene practices in communal living quarters. Outbreaks affecting several soldiers simultaneously are often observed. Transmission vectors include shared footwear, socks, shower mats, dumbbells, and other shared items.

Clinical and Immunological Features. Among military personnel, skin and nail mycoses often present in subclinical or subtle forms. However, under the influence of stress, trauma, and immune suppression, more severe manifestations may occur, including hyperkeratotic, vesicular, and infiltrative types. Immunological research indicates that individuals with chronic and recurrent mycoses experience both innate and adaptive immune response alterations. Key findings include reduced expression of Toll-like receptors (TLR2, TLR4), increased IL-6 and IL-17 levels, decreased IFN- γ production, and impaired Langerhans cell function and Th1 activation. These immune shifts facilitate fungal persistence in skin and nail tissues.

Diagnosis in Military Practice. There is a notable lack of studies focusing on the unique diagnostic challenges of fungal infections in military personnel. This underscores the need to adapt existing diagnostic tools to military conditions, including field exercises and deployments. Despite advancements in medical mycology—such as real-time PCR, MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry, and rapid immunological tests—routine diagnostics in the field often rely on traditional methods, including KOH microscopy, Sabouraud agar culture, chromogenic media, and dermatoscopy. PCR diagnostics allow for pathogen identification and antifungal susceptibility testing within 24-48 hours, which is critical for atypical or resistant infections.

Treatment Approaches. Effective treatment of dermatomycoses in military personnel demands a multifaceted approach that considers clinical form, infection severity, local epidemiology, and the patient's overall condition. Three core therapeutic strategies are emphasized: etiotropic treatment, topical therapy, and immunomodulatory and preventive measures. Etiotropic treatment targets the pathogen directly. Terbinafine is the first-line agent for tinea pedis and onychomycosis due to its high fungicidal activity and bioavailability. Itraconazole exhibits broad-spectrum efficacy against *Candida* spp. and molds, making it suitable for mixed infections. Though less commonly used today, griseofulvin remains relevant for treating tinea capitis, especially in densely populated barrack settings. Topical therapy is appropriate for early-stage or localized infections, as well as an adjunct to systemic treatment. Effective agents include ciclopirox, naftifine, and Exoderil, which demonstrate excellent skin penetration. For onychomycosis, medicated lacquers and keratolytic patches support nail debridement and drug delivery. Immunomodulation and relapse prevention are vital, particularly in high-risk military contexts. Interferon inducers like Anaferon and Polyoxidonium enhance nonspecific immunity. Restoration of the skin microbiome through probiotics and barrier-strengthening agents further reduces reinfection risk. General health support with adaptogens and vitamin complexes (particularly B, C, and D vitamins) is also advised.

Optimization of Treatment Strategies. Optimizing dermatomycosis therapy in military settings requires personalization, selection of effective pharmacological regimens, and integration of preventive strategies. Diagnostic accuracy should be ensured through mycological and molecular testing, particularly PCR, to identify pathogens and guide treatment. Systemic therapy optimization includes the use of terbinafine at standard or escalated doses for tinea pedis and onychomycosis, with response monitoring. Itraconazole is administered in pulse regimens, with hepatic function checks and clinical assessment. Griseofulvin is suitable for scalp infections, with attention to course duration and potential side effects. Topical treatment improvements involve the use of modern formulations with enhanced penetration and long-lasting effects, such as medicated lacquers and patches, improving adherence. Immunomodulatory support is crucial under stress and physical load. Interferon inducers and probiotics enhance host defenses, while adaptogens and vitamins restore immune function.

The unique aspects of military service—high humidity, intense sweating, prolonged wear of uniform clothing and footwear—must be addressed. Recommendations include regular changing of underwear and shoes, routine screenings for fungal infections, and hygiene education for personnel. Promoting awareness and early medical consultation reduces transmission and chronicity. Continuous monitoring of treatment efficacy is essential. Regular clinical assessments and, where feasible, PCR or culture-based testing ensure pathogen eradication and resistance prevention. Footwear and clothing worn in service can create warm, moist environments conducive to fungal growth, particularly *Trichophyton* and *Microsporum* spp. Lack of ventilation and prolonged use without replacement fosters spore accumulation and chronic infection. Evidence from microclimate studies supports preventive actions such as shoe rotation, antifungal treatment of inner surfaces, and hygiene reinforcement. Although direct military-focused studies are limited, strategies proven effective in similar populations should be adapted to military needs.

Prevention and Sanitary-Epidemiological Measures in Military Units. Effective dermatomycosis prevention must begin at enlistment and continue throughout service. Initial medical screening should include foot, nail, and skin inspections to detect early signs of infection. Personal footwear and hygiene kits must be provided. Regular foot hygiene and sock changes are essential, especially after physical activity. Weekly sanitation days with disinfection of shared spaces and UV air recirculators in showers reduce fungal contamination. Educational campaigns—bulletins, commander briefings, hygiene manuals—build awareness and promote early medical engagement. A systematic approach incorporating medical oversight and hygienic protocols is vital to reduce infection risks and maintain sanitary conditions in military environments.

Discussion. Successful management of dermatomycoses in the military requires an interdisciplinary approach involving dermatologists, infectious disease specialists, epidemiologists, and military physicians. Factors such as climate, service branch, daily routine, and field stress influence disease progression and outcomes. Clinical guidelines must be adapted for field realities—shorter treatment courses, adjusted dosages, and minimized side effects are often necessary due to limited medical access. Despite the lack of focused research on uniforms and footwear as fungal reservoirs, related microclimate studies support their role in transmission. Therefore, more attention should be directed toward preventive measures targeting these factors. Immunotherapy, including interferon inducers, plays a key role in relapse prevention. Post-treatment clinical and laboratory monitoring is crucial, especially in chronic or candidal cases, to detect and manage complications.

Conclusion. Dermatomycoses among military personnel constitute a relevant clinical issue requiring a comprehensive diagnostic and therapeutic strategy adapted to military realities. Literature review confirms the efficacy of terbinafine and itraconazole as first-line agents. Equally important are preventive efforts—hygiene control, education, screening, and potentially vaccine development. Though specific studies on uniform-related risk factors are lacking, this area warrants further research. Modern diagnostic tools, including molecular and immunological testing, support a personalized medicine approach, increasing treatment efficacy and reducing recurrence in military healthcare.

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